

An Associated Random Neural Network Detects Intrusions and Estimates Attack Graphs

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Abstract—Cyberattacks, especially Botnet Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), increasingly target networked systems, compromise interconnected nodes by constantly spreading malware. In order to prevent these attacks in their early stages, which includes stopping the spread of malware, it is vital to identify compromised nodes and successfully predict potential attack paths. To this end, this paper proposes a novel system based on an Associated Random Neural Network (ARNN) that simultaneously detects intrusion at the network-level and estimates the network attack graph. In this system, ARNN is trained online to minimize problem-specific multi-task loss so that it identifies compromised network nodes, while the neural network connection weights also estimate the attack path. The performance of the method is calculated using the Kitsune attack dataset, showing that the method achieves a recall rate above 0.95 in estimating the network attack graph, and provides a near-perfect classification of compromised nodes. The ARNN-based system for dynamic and continuous estimation of compromised nodes and network attack graphs, can pave the way for enhancing security measures, and stopping Botnet DDoS attacks from spreading in networked systems.

Index Terms—Cybersecurity, Intrusion Detection, Network Attack Graph, Associated Random Neural Network, Distributed Denial of Service.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, such as those involving Botnets, stand out as prevalent cyber threats targeting networked systems [1]. In 2022, a total increase of 150% in such attacks observed worldwide, with 109% more occurring at the network layer and 72% more occurring at the application layer [2].

Botnet DDoS attacks constantly spread malware throughout the targeted network system, compromising an increasing number of interconnected nodes until the intended goal is achieved. The compromised network nodes, also called “bots”, spread the malware, compromising other nodes and generating malicious traffic.

In order to prevent the spread of malware and mitigate Botnet DDoS attack, it is crucial to identify compromised nodes and estimate the possible paths through which the attack spreads. Hence, the collaboration between intrusion

detection and Network Attack Graph (NAG) estimation is vital for dynamic security measures that will pave the way to develop immune systems against such attacks. NAG estimation improves the understanding of vulnerabilities, weak points, and potential attack paths, while intrusion detection detects security breaches and their locations in the networked system.

A. Related Work

Only few works used machine learning techniques to learn and generate attack graphs or paths directly. Earlier work [3] used Kohonen neural network to learn the attack graph generation from the offline data collected through simulations. The trained neural network is used to obtain a probability that an attacker exploits a vulnerability in a given host. The performance of Kohonen neural network was also compared against the Radial Basis Function (RBF) neural network. In [4], a feed-forward neural network was used to learn from vulnerability dataset and predict the attack graph based on the extracted features. These features were calculated based on the network topology information, system information, and attack path information. The output of that neural network model was binary matrix representing attack graph. On the other hand, the earlier research using machine learning techniques to generate an attack graph requires an available training data on the system vulnerability analysis.

B. Contributions of This Paper

This paper presents a novel system for identifying compromised network nodes and estimating NAG based only on the metrics summarizing the traffic density. Within our system, Associated Random Neural Network (ARNN) [5] is trained sequentially online minimizing the proposed custom multi-task loss to learn the compromised nodes and traces of –normal and malicious– traffic. Training with multi-task loss allows ARNN to learn compromised node identification while its connection weights reflect the attack path as much as possible. The trained ARNN directly provides a network-level intrusion decision on the compromised nodes. Then, based on the ARNN’s intrusion decision, the rate of traffic flow and its connection weights, the estimated NAG is constructed. In this way, our system provides

Fig. 1. Design of the proposed Associated Random Neural Network (ARNN)-based system for compromised node identification and NAG estimation

a dynamic NAG estimation based on real-time network traffic patterns.

Furthermore, the proposed system is experimentally evaluated using the online Kitsune Mirai Botnet attack dataset [6], [7]. The results demonstrate the success of this system, estimating attack paths with recall over 0.95 while classifying compromised nodes near-perfectly.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the methodology of the proposed system, which includes traffic measurements, ARNN structure, sequential online learning, and NAG estimation, respectively. Section III evaluates the performance of the proposed system. Section IV summarizes this paper and provides insights into possible future research directions.

II. IDENTIFYING COMPROMISED NODES AND ESTIMATING NAG SIMULTANEOUSLY

The proposed ARNN-based system, which is shown in Figure 1, operates over time windows of length T . At the beginning of every time window s , ARNN is trained on the historical network traffic data by minimizing the custom multi-task loss. At the end of each window s , trained ARNN is used to estimate the NAG based on the traffic data observed during window s .

A. Traffic Data Processing

Within the proposed system, the network traffic is first processed to extract a single metric for each node n , summarizing the density of the total incoming and outgoing traffic of node n . For each node n in window s , we calculate five different normalized traffic metrics using the collected set of packets:

- Average size of packets received by node n ,
- Maximum size of any packet received by node n ,
- Average number of packets received by node n ,
- Total number of bytes sent by n to all nodes, and
- Total number of packets sent by n to all nodes.

These metrics are the extension of those proposed in recent work [8] to identify compromised network nodes during and ongoing Mirai Botnet attack.

B. ARNN Structure

As the core ML model to estimate the NAG, we use ARNN. The ARNN was specifically designed in [5] for network-wide security assessment and shown to be very successful by experimental performance evaluation. The structure of the ARNN model replicates the structure of the considered network of interconnected nodes. To this end, the ARNN model comprises N ARNN nodes, which are interconnected based on the network's adjacent matrix \mathbf{A} , where all connection are considered bidirectional.

In this paper, we use ARNN with restricted connection weights:

- Any node n is not connected to itself, resulting in $W_{nn}^+ = W_{nn}^- = w_{nn}^+ = w_{nn}^- = 0$.
- The sum of excitatory and inhibitory rates (i.e. connection weights) from a neuron of n to the neurons of other node m equals a fixed constant W_{nm} , so $W_{nm}^+ + W_{nm}^- = w_{nm}^+ + w_{nm}^- = W_{nm}$.

These constraints reduce the number of calculations in the learning algorithm and prevent weights from taking very large values. In addition, prior to the learning of ARNN weights, we initialize all individual weights W_{nm}^+ and w_{nm}^+ randomly from uniform distribution with interval $[0, \sqrt{1/N}]$, which is inspired from He initialization [9]. Then, we set $W_{nm} = 2W_{nm}^+, \forall n, m$.

A binary decision L_n^s stating whether the node n is compromised is obtained as

$$L_n^s = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{Q_n^s(1-q_n^s)}{q_n^s(1-Q_n^s)} > \theta_n \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where Q_n^s and q_n^s are the probabilities that neurons of ARNN node fires spikes.

C. Sequential Attack Graph Learning

Within the proposed system, ARNN learns the communication patterns between network nodes from historical data collected for the last S windows until the beginning of window s . Then, at the end of window s , it estimates NAG based on the traffic data observed in window s . To this end, ARNN is

trained sequentially at the beginning of each window s before which the ARNN performed only estimation for S successive windows. The training algorithm minimizes the proposed multi-task loss through the gradient descent algorithm.

1) *Multi-Task Loss Function*: We first introduce the multi-task loss function, denoted by \mathcal{L}^l , that simultaneously measures the estimation error for both the security states of nodes and attack path over weights for a given learning window l . We let \mathcal{E}^l be the mean square error of ARNN's decisions on the security state of network nodes, and \mathcal{P}^l be the attack path loss over the connection weights. Accordingly, the loss function is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}^l = \frac{1}{2} (\mathcal{E}^l + \mathcal{P}^l). \quad (2)$$

2) *Gradient Descent on Multi-Task Loss*: At the beginning of a time window s for which $(s \bmod S) = 1$, the connection weight matrices W_{uv}^+ and w_{uv}^+ between any pair of connected nodes (u, v) of ARNN are updated via gradient descent algorithm iteratively for each learning window $l \in \{s-1, \dots, s-S\}$ provided in training data:

$$W_{uv}^+ \leftarrow W_{uv}^+ + \eta \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}^l}{\partial W_{uv}^+}, \quad \text{and} \quad w_{uv}^+ \leftarrow w_{uv}^+ + \eta \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}^l}{\partial w_{uv}^+}. \quad (3)$$

After the connection weights are updated for all node pairs (u, v) using the data of all learning windows l , updates via gradient descent in (3) are repeated for a constant number of epochs.

In addition to the learning of ARNN connection weights, we also update the decision threshold θ_n for each node n by selecting –via exhaustive search– the best threshold value that minimizes the ARNN's decision error on the training data.

D. Dynamic Network Attack Graph Estimation

At the end of each time window s , we use ARNN, which has the latest update of the weights, to estimate the NAG based on the connection weights as well as the security state of the individual nodes. To this end, we define a binary variable G_{nm}^s stating whether the connection between nodes n and m were exploited by the attack in window s , where $G_{nm}^s = 1$ indicates that the attack spreads from n to m in window s . Accordingly, G_{nm}^s is calculated as based on the traffic rate, denoted by R_{nm}^s from n to m , the outputs of the ARNN for n , and the connection weights of the ARNN from n to m :

$$G_{nm}^s = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } L_n^s = 1 \text{ and } \left(R_{nm}^s \frac{W_{nm}^+}{w_{nm}^+} > \gamma \right) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where the traffic rate R_{nm}^s is simply calculated as the ratio between the number of packets sent from n to m and the total number of packets received by m . Subsequently, the matrix $\mathbf{G}^s = [G_{nm}^s, \forall n, m]$ constructs the NAG for the current time window s .

III. RESULTS

A. Dataset

During the performance evaluation, we use Mirai Botnet attack data from the open-access dataset Kitsune [6], [7]. This dataset is comprised of 764,137 packets transmitted over 7137 seconds. In this dataset, there are 107 distinct IP addresses in total; however, we consider only the IP addresses in “192.168” network to be able to present a comprehensive and detailed analysis. We set the window length $T = 10$ seconds for which each time window contains approximately 100 packets on average. We also consider that all nodes are interconnected.

The dataset contains only the ground truth as an attack label showing if each packet is malicious or not. Therefore, we first calculate a ground truth regarding the security state of each individual IP address based on the provided attack labels. Then, we determine the ground truth for the NAG using the ground truth for nodes' security states. To this end, the connection from node (IP address) n to m is considered to be exploited if the attack traffic ratio from n to m is higher than the a threshold while both n and m are labeled to be compromised in at least one time window until the end of s .

We now present the ground truth for the NAG calculated for time window $s = 713$, corresponding to the end of the dataset. The ground truth for the NAG at time window $s = 713$ given in Figure 2 shows that the Botnet attack, which has already spread to the majority of nodes, exploited attack paths to nodes 1, 8, 23 and 24, which are some of the few remaining uncompromised nodes. One may expect that the nodes 1, 8, 23 and 24 shall be compromised soon although the dataset covers only up to $s = 713$.

Fig. 2. Ground truth for the NAG at time window $s = 713$, where directed edges indicate the exploited attack path between vertices that can be red and green representing compromised and non-compromised network nodes.

The propagation of the Mirai Botnet attack observed through ground-truth NAGs highlights the importance of detecting intrusions at the network level (i.e., identifying compromised nodes) and simultaneously estimating the NAG with high accuracy.

B. Performance for Compromised Node Identification

Recall that the proposed ARNN-based system simultaneously identifies compromised network nodes and attack paths,

Fig. 3. Number of nodes accurately classified by the ARNN in each time window $s \in \{471, \dots, 713\}$

and the accurate identification of compromised network nodes is crucial for constructing a precise NAG. Therefore, in Figure 3, we briefly present the performance of ARNN for compromised node identification for each time window.

The results in Figure 3 show that the ARNN, which is trained sequentially minimizing the multi-task loss, classifies all nodes perfectly for the majority of time windows. In particular, ARNN misclassifies two nodes in a single window and only one node in six different time windows.

C. Performance for Network Attack Graph Estimation

We now evaluate the performance of the proposed ARNN-based system for its ultimate task of NAG estimation. For the dynamic NAG estimation of ARNN in each time window, we set $\gamma = 0$. For $s = 713$, the estimated NAG is presented in Figure 4. In addition to the actual attack paths provided by the ground truth in Figure 2, ARNN predicts that node 2 likely propagate the attack to uncompromised nodes 15, 17, and 18.

Fig. 4. Network attack graph estimated by ARNN at time window $s = 713$, where directed edges indicate the possibly exploited attack path between vertices that can be red and green representing network nodes identified as compromised and non-compromised

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a novel system for simultaneously predicting compromised network nodes and the network attack

graph—in short, NAG—during the real-time operation of the networked system. The proposed system utilizes traffic metric extraction, NAG construction algorithms, and the Associated Random Neural Network (ARNN) with a sequential training algorithm that minimizes the custom multi-task loss. This system obtains a network-level intrusion decision on the compromised nodes and dynamically constructs an estimated NAG using ARNN’s connection weights. To this end, ARNN continuously learns the relationship between traffic patterns and compromised nodes and attack paths.

We evaluated the performance of our ARNN-based system using the Kitsune Mirai Botnet attack dataset [6], [7]. The evaluation results underscored the effectiveness of the proposed system, achieving a recall rate exceeding 0.95 in estimating attack paths and demonstrating near-perfect classification of compromised nodes. In addition, its reliable performance for various stages of the Botnet attack was also revealed. Future work shall develop a security measure to take preventive actions based on the network-level intrusion decisions and the NAG provided by our ARNN-based system.

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